

THE FUTURE LINGUISTS IN SEARCH FOR THE OPTIMAL CONCEPTION OF SEMANTIC-PHRASEOLOGICAL CORRELATION

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Abstract:

The article dwells on the conception of semantic correlation of English phraseological units on the base of classic English literature.

Key words: phraseological unit, semantics, correlation, context, lexical correlates, occasional phraseological configurations.

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It is widely known that some time Samarkand was the center of the researches on phraseology (now it is the University of Mannheim, Germany). One of the leading theoretical directions on the study of phraseology is still the semantic-stylistic one. Let us consider the results of this conception.

The peculiar and distinctive feature of usage phraseological units in occasional phraseological configurations is the reduction of the common quantity of lexical correlates. Besides, actualization of the semantics of phraseological units has got two peculiarities: a) the revealing of the aspects of the meaning of phraseological units on the base of interaction with both direct and figurative correlates (with homogeneous and manifold lexical units); b) the revealing of the aspects of the meaning of phraseological units with the noticeable prevail of elements of figurative correlation (manifold lexical correlates) of phraseological units. The general quantity of phraseological usage of a second-step correlation exceeds the quantity of phraseological usage with the elements of the first-step correlation of phraseological units.

The reason for reduction of the general quantity of lexical correlates takes place due to the following peculiarities of occasional phraseological configurations:

a) the significantly great contextual notional sufficiency of phraseological units in occasional phraseological configurations rather than in usual configurations with no demand for concretizing and elaboration of the semantics; in other words, occasional conversion of phraseological units from the very beginning makes phraseological unit oriented to the expression of concrete contextual content, and this content is in less demand for the concretizing the meaning;

b) dependence of contextual set of lexemes on techniques of occasional conversion of phraseological unit;

c) tendency of phraseological unit and the context to form comparably notional part of the text within analyzed textual content;

d) great semantic endurance of phraseological units in occasional rather than usual phraseological configurations.

Structural semantic organization of the context, which stipulates the reveal of connotation and inner form of phraseological units is in direct dependence on the elements

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of the first and the second steps of correlation. Their positional and semantic parameters cause the changes in notional content of the whole utterance within inner phrasal, phrasal and upper phrasal types of occasional phraseological configurations.

1. Gladys Barbour was chalk to Hoytie's cheese. She was small and fair whereas Hoytie was tall and dark (N. Goward "The Present Indicative").

2. Ashenden went to the market... stopped in front of the basket, by the side of which, rain or wind, hot or cold, sat that indomitable creature and bought half a pound of butter (W.S. Maugham. Short stories).

In the first example the lexemes, which form correlative antonyms within phrasal context – 'small' – 'tall', 'fair' – 'dark' – are determined by the formal – '(as) different as chalk and cheese' – and the semantic structure of the phraseological unit – 'unlike in essentials, dissimilar'.

The direct interaction on the base of the appropriate types of connection of two antonymic pairs with the semantic of phraseological units form the elements of the first-step correlation. In this situation in the second example, the lexemes "hot or cold" are produced as the elements of the first-step correlation. The semantic content of the lexical unit 'indomitable creature', collateral correlates of phraseological units is used as an addition to the meaning of phraseological unit "rain or wind (fine)" and contextually edged by the meaning of lexical unit 'hot or cold'. The last combination of lexemes is the means that explains the fact of occasional deviation from the norms of usage of phraseological units, e.g. 'indomitable' – 'that cannot be subdued or conquered'.

References:

- [1]. Amriddinova, N. (2022). *The role of context in realization of semantic structure of the text. Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 13, 60-63.
- [2]. Amriddinova, N. S. (2021). *Extra-Linguistic Reasons for Semantic Variation of Phraseologisms. Theoretical & Applied Science Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука*, (9), 652-654.
- [3]. Amriddinova, N. S. (2020). *Some Aspects of Correlation in Semantic Actualization of Phraseological Units. Modern Views and Research*, 183.
- [4]. Bates E. *Language and Context: the Acquisition of pragmatics*. – New York: Academic Press, 2005. – 17- 18 p.
- [5]. Амосова Н.Н. *Основы английской фразеологии*. – Л.: ЛГУ, 1993. – С. 82-84
- [6]. Амриддинова, Н. Ш. (2021). *Peculiarities of Supply and Difficulties in the Research of Variation of Phraseological Meaning in Vocabulary Articles. Международный журнал искусство слова*, 4(6).
- [7]. Амриддинова, Н. Ш. (2011). *Актуализация денотативно-сигнификативной семантики фразеологических единиц (на материале английского языка). Вестник Челябинского государственного университета*, (10), 16-18.
- [8]. Амриддинова, Н. Ш. (2016). *Некоторые особенности формирования американского варианта английского языка. Ученый XXI века*, (2-4).
- [9]. Амриддинова, Н. Ш. *Модификации фразеологического значения как дискуссионная проблема современной лингвистики*.
- [10]. Кунин А.В. *Фразеология современного английского языка*. – М.: МО, 1992. – С.13-15